

Surveying the effect of website's quality on consumer's loyalty on DIGIKALA in Persian Gulf region.

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Abstract

Nowadays, the commercial competition has been increased in many areas of business, especially in electronic business all around the world, hence improvement of the customers' retaining, and enhancement of their loyalty has been more difficult, however, supplying their needs can assist to improve customer's loyalty. The main purpose of the current research is finding the most important factors of continuous purchase of the online shoppers through the commercial websites. In the current research, in order to data gathering, according to surveying on fourteen hypotheses, 384 questionnaires were collected after distributing among responders, so, all hypotheses were approved after analyzing data.

Key words: loyalty, quality of the electronic services, satisfaction, trust, perceived value.

Introduction

In this era of the Web's fascination, people discuss about the business revolution and electronic business, and internet's role in the knowledge-oriented economy. Internet provides a situation for the electronic companies to present on time, accurate, and cheap information to the customers. So, customers can compare prices promptly, and choose the supplier with the best condition (Gounaris et al, 2010). In recent societies, websites have created one of the most important commercial channels and changed the path that the customers try to purchase the products and the services, however, a large number of the consumers prefers to touch products before they purchase them. But with all the comfort, convenience and efficiency of electronic shopping, it results to confront with traditional sale's channels (Nielsen, 2010). Based on the "AIU" ranking that was conducted in 2006 among 67 countries about electronic business, Iran took the 64th rank among those countries (Iran's Department of Commerce, 2008). Therefore, IRAN does not have a good rank in the electronic business. However, according to this information, infrastructure and scientific principles in the field of e-commerce must be expanded, it should be noted that the nascent IT industry in Iran, and the high potential experts and organizations in the formation and development of appropriate expertise and infrastructure in this area are very effective (NikooKar, 1388). Perhaps a part of this problem could be addressed by mistrust, disloyalty and lack of E-shoppers satisfaction. As a consequence, it is so important for researches and e-commerce to understand the effective factors on loyalty, and intention of online repurchase of the customers. Online business has to proper and correct comprehension from buyers' perceptions, and their diverse experiences, because in this environment

purchasers have a second identity as an internet user in addition to their personal identity as a buyer (koufaris, 2002). Most of e-commerce acts based on a business website, and the factors that cause repurchasing among internet users are so varied in comparison with traditional business methods (Wen, 2012). Therefore, the main goal of this research is to find the most important factors of constant usage of e-shoppers from commercial websites. To explain the importance of research's topic, we can present the studies by the experts and elites who believe this subject is important, and want to study on this topics. Statistics from events and facts that are shown by the researchers and experts explain the importance of the current research (Marshal et, al. 1998). Sirgy and Lindquist explain that study on the users' behavior is so critical to commercial success, because the superior comprehension from users' behavior makes an advantage for rivals in internet's sale to provide superior products and services for their customers. Therefore, this process can increase the motivation for customers to conduct e-purchase (Lindquist and Sirgy, 2008). "Zo, Wan and Priobotuk" (2011) focus on the importance of the consumers' loyalty and their tendency to purchase in their studies, because final success of the electronic sale's companies and channels is too depend on constant shopping from the websites. Therefore, retaining an online customer has much less cost rather than finding a new customer. In addition, the study of "Reichheld and Schefter" showed that finding a new customer in the e-business has approximately 20-40 percent more cost rather than acting in the traditional and offline markets (wen, 2012).

Theoretical framework

Electronic service's quality – Satisfaction – Loyalty

In general, quality of service is identified as a perceived difference between customer's expectation and their evaluation from their obtainment (Parasuraman et al., 1988). In addition, satisfaction and happiness of customers means customers' opinions and judgments about a particular purchase. Satisfaction means the customer's judgments about the value that they received (Mansouri,2009). Also, in some cases, the satisfaction is defined as the feel or approach of a person that effects on particular situation in relation with various factors (Wixom & Todd,2005). The research literature of quality of service supports this context that perceptions of quality of service will result in an improvement in customer satisfaction, therefore, customers' satisfaction is created by comparison and accordance between perceived quality and expected quality (Sivadas & Prewitt,2000). In electronic environment, recent researches confirm that electronic quality influences on satisfaction (Shamdasuui,2008). Also, according to Bagozi's opinion, however, surveying the quality of products and services causes an emotional state about satisfaction, this factor motivates behavioral intentions and the loyalty of the customers (Bagozi,1992). Furthermore, Brady and Robertson studied the casual relations among quality, satisfaction and loyalty, and the results confirm the direct relations between these factors (Brady & Robertson, 2001). In addition, according to other studies, there are direct relations among quality of electronic services, perceived value, satisfaction, purchase intention, and the loyalty of the customers (Kim & Kim, 2010).

H1: Quality of the electronic services effects on customer's satisfaction

H2: Quality of the electronic services effects on customer's loyalty

H3: Quality of electronic services effects on perceived value.

H4: Satisfaction effects on customer's loyalty.

Perceived value

Marketing acts usually based on the perceived value by the customers. Perceived value identified based on the customer's assessment from costs and obtained profits from purchase of the products and services (yang, 2004). Results of some researches imply that perceived value increases customers' satisfaction, customers' loyalty, and future purchases (Jenkins, 2010). Perceived value is a factor that comes after perceived quality, and perceived quality can be thought as a precondition for value (Zins, 2001). It should be noted that the concepts of satisfaction and loyalty are two strong predictor factors about

client's retention, continued trade with the supplier of customer service, or repurchase from a specific brand (Olsen, 2003).

H5: Perceived value effects on trust.

H6: Perceived value effects on customer's satisfaction.

H7: Perceived value effects on customer's loyalty.

Trust-Loyalty

Trust occurs when a group confides about the credit and the honesty of their partners or other parties in a deal (Morgan,1994). In fact, the trust is an interest to rely on a reliable trading partner (Zaltman,1992). Presenting this factor to the customers, that the company cares them and wants to assist them, creates, helps and reinforces a trust-inspiring relation that attracts customers' loyalty (Landerson,2003).

Besides, trust can be considered as a consequence of positive evaluation of perceived services, and a subsequent of the customers' loyalty. Actually, when the customers don't have a trust to the supplier's competency and honesty, they are not interested in commitment to the services (Gummerus, 2004).

H8: Trust effects on customer's loyalty.

Loyalty

A loyal customer is committed and depended about an organization, and doesn't tend to other organizations easily, resists against alternation and change, shows more intention to buy, and acts more flexible against higher prices (Reichheld&Schefter, 2000). On the other hand, loyalty as a customer's desired attitude toward an electronic business causes behavior of repurchase (Anderson &Srinivasan, 2003). In addition, loyalty and its effect on oral advertisements almost are in focused, and one of the expected results from electronic loyalty is positive oral advertisement (Wirtz and Chew, 2002).

H9:Customer's loyalty effects on customer's repurchase intention.

H10:Customer's loyalty effects on customer word of mouth.

H11:Customer's loyalty effects on tend to pay more.

Figure 1: research's conceptual framework1

(Wen,2012,68) Wen, Chao. *The Impact of Quality on Customer Behavioral Intentions Based on the Consumer Decision Making Process As Applied in E-commerce.* Denton, Texas

Methodology

The purpose of choosing Methodology is finding the method or technique that drives the researcher to the possible answers more accurately and easily. Methodology is depended to goals, nature of subject and facilities and resources (Naderi, 1380, 5).

Various classifications of Methodology has been conducted from the viewpoint of experts. One of these classification is intentionally classification and other one is classification by method, because findings from these two kinds can be used to solve executive issues. However, current research is applied-oriented research according to the purpose, it is a descriptive-surveying research according to nature, because data collecting has been done by questionnaire tools. Although, the thematic scope of this research is in field of marketing management, spatial scope is on the website of "DIGIKALA" in Persian Gulf region. The time scope is cross-sectional, because the questionnaire distributed and collected in Jun 2014, and it had been done between February 2014, and August 2014. Statistic society in current survey is all on-line customers were visiting this website in Persian Gulf region to purchase the products. In addition, 384 samples was chosen according to Morgan's table, because the society in this research is wildly, and it is called unlimited society. The questionnaire of the present study has been designed

based on standard-related questionnaires, and the research's literature about variables of this study. To design this questionnaire, Likert's scale that is one of the most common measurement's tools was used. In general form, this scale's rating is from "very high" with 5 scores, to "Very low" with 1 score.

Questionnaire validity means how the researcher can be sure the data collecting's tool measures the desired concept and no other things. In other words, whether the measurement's tools can measure the characteristic which it is intended to evaluate or not (Sekaran, 2004, 223). Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the validity of the present study. For this purpose, a pre-test sample contains 30 questionnaire had been tested firstly, then Cronbach's alpha reliability's coefficient for this tool was calculated by gathered data with SPSS software. As a consequence, the Validity of questionnaire was good, because the Cronbach's Alpha of pre-test sample was more than 0.7.

Table1: validity

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.941	15

Questionnaire Reliability

The reliability is one of the technical characteristics of the instrument. It means to what extent the measurement's instrument gives a same results in same conditions. In the current survey, the "split-half" method was used to evaluate the reliability of the questionnaire. The results approved a good reliability of questionnaire, because the relevant coefficient in the part of "Guttman Split-half" was 0.92.

Reliability Statistics	
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient	.920

Table2: Reliability Statistics

Data analyze method and test of hypothesis

Descriptive and inferential statistics methods were used to data analyze in current survey. However, descriptive statistics indexes, central indexes (mean, mode and median) and statistical dispersion (standard deviation and variance), was used to survey the responders' characteristics. Dedicational statistical methods was used

to test of hypothesis. To determine the normality of the data distribution, "Kolmogorov-Smirnov" test was used. The conducted test, showed collected data did not had "Normal" distribution. In fact, regarding to the rate of "Asymp.sig" of tested data was less than 0.05, H_0 hypotheses of the research that indicates to normality of the data has not been confirmed, therefore data had non-normal distribution. So, nonparametric tests must been used to test of the hypotheses of the research. Therefore, nonparametric marked ranked test, "Wilcoxon", is used to test the research hypotheses. This test is a nonparametric test that is equivalent to T test, then if there isn't a proper condition to T test, it could be a good alternative. In addition, in current research another questionnaire was distributed to analyze by Lisrel software that analyzed results will be presented in follow.

Results

Based on the collected data, 2.1 percent of responders were in the under twenty years' group, however, the age group of 20-40 years old contains 89.6%. In addition, 7.6 percent belonged to the age group of 41-60, and ultimately just 0.8 percent of responders placed in the group of above 61 years old. The mean of age of responder was 30 years old, median was 27.5 and mode was 26 years old. Most young people in the sample was 14, and the oldest person had 70 years old. Furthermore, 51 percent of participant had Bachelor degree, 41 percent had Master degree or PhD, and just 8 percent had Diploma. 49 percent of responders worked in private section, and 12 percent in governmental section. 15 percent of participant were out of job. 3 percent were Housewife and 3 percent were retired, although 18 percent of samples chose other option that it means they did not declare their income's resource, but they had job.

Table3: Results

Hypotheses	Results based on the Wilcoxon test
1. Quality of the electronic services effects on customer's satisfaction.	Approved
2. Quality of the electronic services effects on customer's loyalty	Approved
3. Quality of electronic services effects on perceived value.	Approved

4. Satisfaction effects on customer's loyalty	Approved
5. Perceived value effects on trust.	Approved
6. Perceived value effects on customer's satisfaction.	Approved
7. Perceived value effects on customer's loyalty.	Approved
8. Trust effects on customer's loyalty.	Approved
9. Customer's loyalty effects on customer's repurchase intention.	Approved
10. Customer's loyalty effects on customer WOM.	Approved
11. Customer's loyalty effects on tend to pay more.	Approved

As regards, in current research the second questionnaire was used to path analyze with Lisrel software.

In the current survey, before implementation of path analyzes, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) have been used.

Ultimately, for surveying the research's hypotheses, path analyzes is used, so the structural model of the research in meaningful mode can be seen in the chart below.

Figure 1: Structural Model in the Standard Mode

Table4: Results

Hypothesis	Meaningful level	Result
1	6.86	Approved
2	8.81	Approved
3	3.40	Approved
4	6.88	Approved
5	9.02	Approved
6	4.73	Approved
7	8.24	Approved
8	12.73	Approved
9	6.63	Approved
10	15.12	Approved
11	8.83	Approved

According to the chart, the first hypothesis is approved, because the meaningful number is more than 1.96 (6.82>1.96), hence the Electronic service quality has a direct, meaningful effect on Satisfaction.

The second hypothesis is approved, because the meaningful number is more than 1.96 (8.81>1.96). Thus the Electronic service quality has a direct, meaningful influence on the Brand loyalty.

The third hypothesis is approved, because the meaningful number is more than 1.96 (3.40>1.96), hence the Electronic service quality has a direct, meaningful effect on Perceived value

The fourth hypothesis is approved, by the meaningful number, because it is more than 1.96 (6.88>1.96). Hence the Satisfaction has a direct, meaningful effect on Loyalty.

The fifth hypothesis is approved, by the meaningful number, because it is more than 1.96 (9.02>1.96). Hence the Perceived value has a direct, meaningful effect on Trust.

The sixth hypothesis is approved, by the meaningful number, because it is more than 1.96 (4.73>1.96). Hence the Perceived value has a direct, meaningful effect on Satisfaction.

The seventh hypothesis is approved, by the meaningful number, because it is more than 1.96 (8.24>1.96). Hence the Perceived value has a direct, meaningful effect on Loyalty.

The eighth hypothesis is approved, by the meaningful number, because it is more than 1.96 (12.37>1.96). Hence the trust has a direct, meaningful effect on Loyalty.

The ninth hypothesis is approved, by the meaningful number, because it is more than 1.96 (6.63>1.96). Hence the Loyalty has a direct, meaningful effect on repurchase intention.

The tenth hypothesis is approved, by the meaningful number, because it is more than 1.96 (15.12>1.96). Hence the Loyalty has a direct, meaningful effect on word of mouth.

The eleventh hypothesis is approved, by the meaningful number, because it is more than 1.96 (8.38>1.96). Hence the Loyalty has a direct, meaningful effect on pay more.

The research results are depicted in the table below in the summary.

LISREL software represented some adequate indexes about fitting model indexes; therefore the general fitting index of the model can be tested by using them. The amount of these indexes in current research is more than the average, therefore this model is acceptable according to this index.

Table 5: fitting model indexes

Index	Amount
X ²	253.08
Df	109
RMSEA	0.058
GFI	0.92
AGFI	0.91
NFI	0.9
X ² /df	2.36

Discussion

According to the first theses, perceived quality of website is related to customer’s satisfaction, and this perception comes from a comparison between

expectations and actual performance (Parasuraman et, al.1988). In addition, “Bagozi” believes surveying the quality of products causes to an emotional state about satisfaction, and this factor drives behavioral intentions of customers (Bagozi, 1992), and “Brady and Robertson” studied casual relations between quality, satisfaction, and loyalty, that its results conformed with mentioned relations (Brady & Robertson,2001).

The achieved results from the second hypothesis represent the quality of electronic service effects on customer’s satisfaction to repurchase the products from the website. According to “Kuo et al,” quality of service effects positively on perceived value, and then perceived value influences on customer’s satisfaction and after-buy intention positively. In addition, satisfaction influences on after-buy intention positively too, therefore, quality of service has a positive indirect effect on after-buy intention through customer’s satisfaction or perceived value (Kuo and et al, 2009, 887).

According to the third theses, results approve that the quality of the electronic service effects on perceived value by customer. Achieved results demonstrate that quality of electronic service, such as website’s quality, money transfer and support, influences on the value that customer believes obtained it from transacting with company. Also, in 1987, “Buzzel and Ate” said quality of past services not only has effect on organization’s Profitability, but also it is related on organization’s growth, because of the effect of quality on the perceived value. In addition, Zeithaml, and his colleagues conducted a survey in U.S, and they concluded that services’ companies have particular sensitivity to the quality of services, because high quality can be a key to distinction, increase in customer’s perceived value, and utilization and efficiency of the organizations (Chang, 1998, 248).

According to results related to fourth hypothesis, the customer’s satisfaction from his relation with the website effects on his loyalty and his actions such as repetition in his purchase. However, the study of “Chau Wan”, 2012, confirmed this relation, according to the analysis of "Oliver" (1999), satisfaction is the first essential phase in making loyalty; but other factors such as personal decision (or certainty) and social integration can influence on relationships of customers with organizations indeed. In addition, Duffy’s study indicated there is a direct relation between customers’ satisfaction and their loyalty. It means that the satisfied customers be loyal, and dissatisfied customers go to other vendors. Usually satisfaction is used as a predictor of company’s future buys. It is likely that satisfied customers repeat their buys, and customers, who were

satisfied, will be deluded less by the competitors. Satisfaction has been identified as first essentiality of loyalty (Duffy, 2005, 284).

Regarding to fifth theses, results demonstrate the value that the customer perceives from transacting with the website, influences on created trust on customer. “Chau wan’s” study, conducted in 2012, approves this relation.

The results from sixth hypothesis indicate that perceived value, from a transacting with a website, effects on customer’s satisfaction. The study of “Chau van”, conducted in 2012, approves this hypothesis too. In addition, according to another study, “Lanchard and Galvy” believe that customer’s satisfaction stems from customer’s perception from a transaction or valuable relationship, so that the price is equal to the ratio of quality to price and customer’s costs (Hallowell, 1996, 28).

The results related to the seventh hypothesis show the perceived value from a transaction with a website effects on customer’s loyalty to the website; although, the study of “Chau van”, conducted in 2012, approves this hypothesis too.

The results from eighth hypothesis declare, the trust that the customers has about the website, effects on his loyalty and his actions, such as repetition in his purchase. The study of “Chau Wan”, 2012, confirmed this relation indeed.

The results related to ninth hypothesis of current research indicate the caused feel of loyalty about the website encourages the repurchase action by customer, although this relation was approved by Chau wan’s study, 2012. Furthermore, according to “Larson and Susana”, 2004, loyalty makes a deep commitment to repurchase a superior product or service again in the future that means buying again the brand, despite competitors’ environmental influences and marketing efforts to change the behavior (Abdulvand and Abdul, 2008,8).

Regarding to tenth hypothesis, results show the caused feel of loyalty about the website motivates the customer to promote for the website in his belonged social circles, indeed, this relation was approved in study of Chau Wan, 2012.

The results about the eleventh hypothesis indicate that created feel of loyalty from the website causes lavishly spent for paying the products’ cost by the customer, and increases the number of purchase which customer intends to buy from the website. This relation was approved in Chau Wan’s study, in 2012, too.

Suggestions

We tried to provide suggestions to improve actions in e-business by taking a closer look to gathered data from provided questionnaire, in addition, we tried to present suggestion based on obtained facts from current study and avoid to involve personal opinions. All hypotheses about the quality, such as quality of site, money transfer's quality, and quality of support and their effects on satisfaction, loyalty, and perceived value of the customers have been approved, therefore, it is suggested to "DIGIKALA's" managers to put the maintenance and promoting measures on three indicators of quality, contain website's quality, money transfer's quality and support quality in their agenda. In addition, according to the respondents, the highest effect in relation to the impact on the quality had been expressed as effectiveness of website's quality (67.2%), it is suggested to DIGIKALA's managers to consider the improvement of this factor more than other variables.

All hypotheses about the effectiveness of customer's perceived value on variables of loyalty, satisfaction and trust have been confirmed in current study. Hence, it is suggested to managers of "DIGIKALA" to assist to improve the conditions of mentioned variables with increased focus on the factors that contribute to enhance customer's perceived value. Furthermore, as regard to respondent's opinion that expressed the most influential factor about the effect of perceived value is on ratio of loyalty (68%), therefore, it is suggested to DIGIKALA's managers to consider it adequately.

All hypotheses about the effect of loyalty on three variables, including tend to repurchase, mouth to mouth advertisement, and willingness to pay more, have been approved, by considering these relations, thus, it is suggested to managers that take step toward a growth and improvement of their customers' loyalty, and then improvement in sale. However, according to this fact that respondents believed most effective factor in relation with loyalty's effect is easiness and willingness to pay more (69.5%), it is suggested that managers improve the sale's rate and loyalty through this way.

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